

Best Practices and Mesh Convergence on the Extruded Imperial Front Wing with CharLES Solver

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Abstract

In the present study, we carry out CFD simulations on an extruded 2D slice of the Imperial Front Wing configuration at $Re = 220'000$ (based on the front wing chord). The focus is on best practices necessary to run accurate LES simulations on the present configuration with the CharLES solver. The low Mach number Finite Volume CharLES solver, generally used for automotive configurations, is the main solver for this study. As a reference we use the Wall Resolved LES results with Nektar++[1]. The initial simulation is carried out at a mesh resolution requiring the usage of Wall Models ($y^+ \approx 15 - 20$), but which can run 30CTUs within 5 hours on 384 cores. While the lift coefficient is in line with the reference ($C_L = -8.11$ vs $C_{L,ref} = -8.33$), the physics related to the laminar separation bubbles (LSBs) on the wing elements and the laminar to turbulent transition are not captured at wall model resolution. To improve the results we put forward a set of hypothesis and verify whether these hypothesis impact the results positively. The following tests are carried out : 1) wall normal mesh resolution 2) $y^+ < 1$ 3) STL quality 4) wall model activation at wall resolved resolution 5) sub grid scale Model (SGS) choice 6) time step impact 7) side wall boundary conditions 8) aspect ratio. To verify the quality of the result the following metrics are used : lift and drag coefficients, centerline Cp and Cf plots, power spectral density (PSD) of signals (local velocity, local Cp, lift and drag coefficient) and wake velocity profiles.

During the mesh convergence study (section 4.1: hypothesis 1), we observe that in order to capture the compressed upcoming laminar boundary layer, a $y^+ \approx 5$ (exchange layer in viscous sublayer) is necessary in order to accurately reproduce the C_f profile upstream of the laminar separation bubbles (LSBs) and have a laminar to turbulent transition, albeit too far upstream. For the LSBs on the three wing elements, a $y^+ \approx 2.5$ is necessary, combined with a low aspect ratio mesh as shown in section 4.5. The choice of an appropriate aspect ratio and growth rate is explored in section 4.7, but this would ideally still require further investigation. With regards to the wake, we observe that Wall Resolved LES resolution is not necessary to capture the velocity profiles in the wake accurately (section 4.8).

The verification of the various hypothesis thus provides us with information about the necessary mesh resolution and other solver options necessary to reproduce the reference wall resolved results obtained with Nektar++.

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Introduction

As means of transport get faster, aerodynamics becomes the dominant source of friction and consequently an important field of research. The domain most affected by aerodynamics is probably aviation, but the automotive sector is also vital, especially considering the carbon emissions of transport. One such automotive industry, where aerodynamics plays an even more crucial role, is F1 racing. The ability to generate large amounts of downforce while minimising drag is crucial. Since F1 related designs are not widely available we will use the Imperial Front Wing (IFW) which is based on the McLaren 17D from 2003. In a previous study [2], we showed how different simulation methodologies performed on the full 3D IFW and compared them with previous experimental and CFD study [3].

For this study, we focus on the 2D Extruded IFW slice which was run with the LES High Order Nektar++ code [1] at $Re = 220'000$ (based on the Imperial Front Wing's mainplane chord length) and by Ntoukas [4] on a mesh with fewer degrees of freedom. The focus of the study is to establish best practices (meshing resolution and other settings) to run accurate Large Eddy Simulations (LES) with the Finite Volume CharLES solver. As shown in [1], the extruded IFW case has features which are present at Wall Resolved LES resolution, such as the laminar separation bubble on the suction side of the mainplane and the first flap, the laminar separation bubble on the pressure side of the second flap, the transition mechanism of each wing element, the wake momentum deficit, etc... We will thus be trying to answer what spatial resolution and other parameters (e.g. time step, Sub Grid Scale model, etc...) are necessary to accurately reproduce each of the features.

This study starts off with a base mesh that requires the usage of wall models to model the near wall physics. As can be expected based on the previous research [1] [4] on this test case, a much more refined mesh resolution is required. As such a mesh convergence study is carried out in section 4.1 where we lower the wall normal cell height (and increase the aspect ratio for computational cost reasons) down to $y^+ \approx 1$. This is hypothesis 1, which states that $y^+ \approx 1$ is necessary to capture the physics. This mesh resolution is however not sufficient, which forces us to further investigate, to put forward a set of hypothesis and verify whether they impact the results positively and allow us to capture the near wall physics. These include the effect of the imported CAD file quality (hypothesis 3), the usage of wall model on low y^+ meshes (hypothesis 4), the effect of the Vreman sub grid scale model (hypothesis 5), the time step size effect (hypothesis 6), the effect of periodic vs slip side walls (hypothesis 7) and finally the effect of the aspect ratio and the growth rate which is covered by hypothesis 2, hypothesis 8 and the open ended investigation in section 4.7. In section 5 we give mesh recommendations and best practices to run F1 front wing configuration with CharLES before ending with the conclusion.

These findings will then be used to run the full 3D Imperial Front Wing in future work.

1 Case Description

The 2D Extruded Imperial Front Wing configuration is based on a $y = -250\text{mm}$ slice of the full 3D Imperial Front Wing on which several studies have been carried out such as [3], [5] and [2]. The original 3D setup at Imperial College (see Fig.1) used $h/c = 0.36$ which can be considered a low ride height, with significant ground effect and thus high downforce levels. The $Re = 220'000$ is kept the same as for the full 3D setup.

Figure 1: IFW geometry and nomenclature [3]: chord length c (yellow line), ride height h , nose cone (A), Gurney Flap (B), canard (C), endplate (D) and footplate (E)

1.1 CFD IFW Domain Setup

For the CFD simulations, the geometry is based on a 2D slice of the original 3D Imperial Front Wing. The geometry is then extruded in the third dimension with a span of $0.16c = 0.04\text{m}$. The dimensions of the domain are shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: CFD Domain of the 2D Extruded Imperial Front Wing

The following boundary conditions are the default (unless specified otherwise in the following sections):

- Inlet : $u_x = U_{inf} = 12.5\text{m/s}$
- Floor : moving floor $u_x = U_{inf} = 12.5\text{m/s}$
- Ceiling : slip BC
- Side Walls : slip BC
- Outlet : low-mach non-reflecting outflow with Mach = 0.036 (based on $u = 12.5\text{m/s}$)
- IFW : Algebraic Wall Model (WM_ALG)

2 Wall Model LES / CharLES

For the present study we are only using the low mach CharLES solver [6] from Cadence Design Systems. This Finite Volume pressure based solver is an appropriate choice for Large Eddy Simulations of complex geometries at high Reynolds number thanks to the usage of wall models [7] which make LES more computationally affordable. Accurate LES simulations require the mesh to resolve a large portion of length scales found in a turbulent flow. However, as we move closer to the boundaries this constraint becomes very costly since the mean eddies size get smaller until we reach the viscous sub-layer. If we resolve the eddies down to the wall, we are running a wall resolved LES (WRLES) which would require far more near wall mesh resolution and the usage of a smaller time step to ensure stability.

In a wall model approach, the near wall behaviour is modelled rather than resolved. Within the large family of wall modelling approaches that exist, the one used with CharLES on this test case is the algebraic wall model. For this we assume that the flow is parallel to the wall at first cell height cell centre and that the law of the wall can be applied to the behaviour within the first cell. The simple algebraic wall model comes from the integration of the equilibrium stress model [8] :

$$u^+(y^+) = \begin{cases} y^+ + a_1(y^+)^2 & \text{for } y^+ < 23, \\ \frac{1}{\kappa} \ln y^+ + B & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where $B = 5.2$ and a_1 ensure C^1 continuity. The effects of unsteadiness or pressure gradients in the inner layer are not taken into account in these models. An iterative solver is then used to find

the wall shear stress and then used to set a Neumann boundary condition at the wall where the algebraic wall model is set. The default Vreman [9] sub grid scale model is for the solver.

An in house mesh generation tool called *stitch* generates a polyhedral mesh defined by a Voronoi diagram (see Fig. 3a) which is used by the solver.

For the boundary layer a structured mesh is used by calling the STRAND option from *stitch* which allows the user to generate a RANS like mesh which can be used to run Wall Resolved LES if the Reynolds is sufficiently low and the computational resources are sufficient. A example of what this type of mesh looks like near the leading edge of the 1st flap is shown in Fig. 3b.

Figure 3: Polyhedral mesh defined by a Voronoi diagram

3 Mesh Setup

As just mentioned, for running the CharLES simulation, a polyhedral mesh created by the in house *stitch* mesher was used with the Cartesian option on.

Since the extrusion of the 2D slice is 16% of the chord length or 0.04m, we need a sufficient number cells in the third dimension. A base cell size of $h = 0.008\text{m}$, which allows for 5 cell across the span, was chosen. Since the volume of the domain is 2.4m^3 ($20\text{m} \times 3\text{m} \times 0.04\text{m}$), this results in approximately 4.7 million cells before placing any wake refinement boxes or near wall refinement. Three different volume refinement boxes which are kept the same for all the simulations are placed around the body and in the wake for which the parameters are given in Table 1.

STRAND Mesh parameters					
Ref. box	x range	z range	Wake Level	Cell Size	\approx Millions of Cells
IFW Box	[-0.9,-0.3]	[0.025,0.25]	3	0.001m	5.4
Wake Box	[-1.2,2]	[-0.025,0.550]	2	0.002m	9.2
Far wake Box	[2,4]	[-0.025,0.55]	1	0.004m	0.7

Table 1: Table summarising the volume refinement boxes. Leading edge of the mainplane is at $x = -0.85\text{m}$ and the mainplane chord length is $c = 0.25\text{m}$

For resolving/modelling the boundary layer behaviour, the STRAND option is used to create a structured mesh around the body and decrease the computational cost by using non isotropic elements. These are the mesh settings that are changed for all the meshes. For the study we start off with a higher y^+ mesh that requires the usage of wall models but with enough resolution between the wing elements (e.g. 10-12 cells) and low aspect ratio mesh ($As = 2$). This results in Mesh 1 having a $y^+ \approx 17$ at the location of the laminar to turbulent transition, an aspect ratio of 2, 10 layers in the STRAND and a growth rate of 1.08. Mesh 2 uses a $y^+ \approx 5$ at the laminar to turbulent transition location, a higher aspect ratio to keep the cell count under control. Mesh 7 lowers the y^+ to 1, keeps the aspect ratio at 5 which results in the mesh having 87 million cells. In hypothesis 7, we will show that this mesh is not capable of capturing the mainplane laminar separation bubble. As such many meshes were tested until we ran Mesh 32 which was capable of capturing the physics with $y^+ \approx 2.5$ but a lower aspect ratio, more cells in the STRAND height and therefore a lower growth rate.

Fig. 4 compares Mesh 1, Mesh 2 and Mesh 7 in the gap between the trailing edge of the mainplane and the 1st flap. We clearly see the structured STRAND mesh as we refine the mesh that converges towards a wall resolved LES mesh.

Figure 4: Comparison of the Vorνοι meshes near the gap between the mainplane and the 1st flap

The boundary layer mesh parameters for Mesh 1, Mesh 2, Mesh 7 and Mesh 32 are shown in Table 2. The floor doesn't use the STRAND option but keeps the isotropic volume mesh since this is a part where we wish to keep the WMLES behaviour in order to keep the costs low and only focus on the mesh converges around the IFW body. Additional surface refinement is added to capture the sharp gradient near the floor since we have ground effects.

Mesh Setup					
Element	Parameter	Mesh 1	Mesh 2	Mesh 7	Mesh 32
IFW	1st cell height [m]	5e-4	1e-4	2e-5	5e-5
IFW	Nb of layers	10	10	12	20
IFW	Growth Rate	1.08	1.2	1.16	1.036
IFW	y^+	15-20	5	1	2.5
IFW	Apect ratio	2	5	5	2
IFW	Strand height	0.00725m	0.0025m	0.0006m	0.0015m
Floor	1st cell height[m]	5e-4	5e-4	5e-4	1.25e-4
Floor	y^+	?	?	?	?
Floor	Aspect ratio	1	1	1	1
Floor	NLayers	2	2	2	4
	Nb Cells	21M	23M	87M	160M

Table 2: Mesh Parameters used for the CharLES simulations. The NLayers parameters controls how smoothly refinement boxes/surfaces diffuse into the background mesh.

After having captured the physics properly with Mesh 32 (demonstrated in section 4.5 of the Results), we carry out an aspect ratio and growth rate investigation at WRLES resolution in section 4.7, where we only change the parameters of the STRAND option to investigate its effect. The meshes and parameters used for this study are summarised in Table 3.

STRAND Mesh parameters					
Mesh	y^+	Aspect Ratio	Nb Layers Profile	Growth Rate	Cells within LSB height
Mesh 7	1	5	12	1.16	7
Mesh 32	2.5	2	20	1.036	4
Mesh 33	2.5	2	7	1.12	3
Mesh 34	2.5	2	10	1.08	4
Mesh 35	1.6	3	20	1.06	6
Mesh 36	1	5	20	1.088	8

Table 3: Table summarising the meshes used for the aspect ratio and growth rate investigation at WRLES resolution in section 4.7

4 Results

In the results section, we cover all the results obtained on the extruded IFW setup with CharLES in order to help us establish guidelines to capture different physical features correctly. We start off with a baseline mesh (Mesh 1) which uses an algebraic wall model to model the boundary conditions. However as we will show in section 4.1 this resolution isn't sufficient to capture the physics correctly.

We therefore put forward a set of hypothesis which we believe will either improve the results or for which we wish to confirm the negligible impact. To quantify the impact of the mesh or parameter changes of each hypothesis, we compare the impact on the integrated forces, the C_p centerline profile and the C_f centerline profiles. The impact on the wake velocity profiles will be shown separately in section 4.8.

Once we achieve accurate results with a given mesh (i.e. Mesh 32) and set of parameters (boundary conditions, sub grid scale model, time step etc...), we explore the neighbourhood of mesh parameters similar to Mesh 32 in order to establish meshing criteria necessary to capture the physics completely.

With all of this information we can establish best practices to fully capture the physics and give mesh resolution recommendations if the user isn't interested in capturing all the physical features of the flow which might be too computationally expensive.

Velocity and pressure probes were added at many locations approximately one cell height off the wall around the IFW in order to identify whether local wall shear stress had reached a statistically stationary state and also to identify the main modes and compare with those found in [1]. This data has not been collected for all the simulations and will therefore only be show when relevant.

4.1 Hypothesis 1 (Wall Normal Resolution)

Hypothesis 1 states that we need to resolve the eddies down to the wall to capture the laminar separation bubbles. Let's therefore verify this hypothesis by comparing results at three different near wall mesh resolutions : $y^+ \approx 15 - 20$, $y^+ \approx 5$ and $y^+ \approx 1$.

4.1.1 Lift and Drag Coefficients

Firstly let us see how improving the wall normal resolution impacts the integrated forces. In Fig. 5 we compare the drag coefficient signal and spectrum for the three meshes. By observing the signal we can see that the mean drag converges monotonically towards the reference as we reduce the first cell height. The relative error decreases from 22% for Mesh 1 to an 8% error for Mesh 7 with respect to the Nektar++ reference. For the spectrum, we observe more energy in the higher frequency oscillations beyond $St = 100$ as we refine the mesh. A peak at $St \approx 25$ is observed for Mesh 7 which doesn't appear for the coarser meshes. But overall the spectrum hasn't changed too significantly.

Figure 5: Drag Coefficient signal and spectrum

For lift coefficient on the other hand we do not observe a monotonic convergence of the forces as we reduce the first cell height. In fact Mesh 2 has the highest relative error (rel. error 3.7%) compared to the reference, while Mesh 7 has the smallest relative error (rel. error 1.6%). By observing the C_p profiles we will be able to pinpoint where the differences are coming from. For the spectrum of lift a similar behaviour is observed as for drag with a peak at $St \approx 25$ and less energy at the higher frequencies on coarser meshes.

Figure 6: Lift Coefficient signal and spectrum

4.1.2 C_p Profiles

As we just showed, differences in the integrated forces can be noticed as we refine the mesh. Since the pressure contribution is more significant than the viscous for the F1 wings, looking at the centerline C_p profiles will help us identify which parts benefited the most from the mesh refinement. In Fig. 7 we can see how the C_p profile is impacted on the mainplane. As can be seen the pressure side doesn't benefit from the more resolved mesh resolution, however on the suction side we notice mesh convergence towards the Nektar++ reference profile. A peak negative $C_p \approx -11$ is present near the leading edge, while the strong adverse pressure is present on the suction side.

Figure 7: C_p Profile Mainplane

In Fig. 8a, we show the C_p profile on the 1st flap. Once again the pressure side doesn't benefit from additional mesh resolution. On the suction side however we notice improvements as we refine the mesh. Once we reach $y^+ \approx 1$ we notice the fairly constant adverse pressure gradient on the suction side which is interrupted by a flattening out and then a sharp increase in C_p at around $x \approx -0.55$ (location where the rear of the laminar separation bubble should be). On the second flap (see Fig. 8b), the adverse pressure gradient on the suction side appears to be monotone and not benefit from mesh resolution. On the pressure side however, the sharp increase in C_p is only present for the $y^+ \approx 1$ mesh. It is however further upstream compared to the Nektar++ reference, indicating potentially that our LSB is further upstream than in the reference.

Figure 8: C_p Profile

4.1.3 C_f Profiles

In this section we will show the changes observed on the mean non-dimensional wall shear stress of the various wing elements. While the C_p profiles help identify where the difference in integrated forces come from and the location of the laminar separation bubbles, the C_f profile magnifies those differences and help locate the position of the LSBs and transition locations. In Fig. 9, we illustrate the convergence of the C_f profile as we refine the near wall resolution from $y^+ \approx 15 - 20$ to $y^+ \approx 5$ to $y^+ \approx 1$. We can notice that mesh 1 ($y^+ \approx 15 - 20$) performs well on the pressure side but poorly on the suction side, particularly for the upcoming laminar boundary layer where it overestimates significantly the wall shear stress. As we refine the mesh to $y^+ \approx 5$ (mesh 2), we notice that the issue for the upcoming laminar boundary layer is resolved, but the laminar separation bubble isn't predicted since $C_f > 0$ and therefore no stagnation point is found (stagnation point has $C_f = 0$).

As we refine further, we notice that the C_f is converging towards the Nektar++ reference, but hasn't predicted the LSB yet.

Figure 9: Mean wall shear stress magnitude on the mainplane

The mean non-dimensional wall shear stress C_f centerline profiles are shown for the 1st flap in Fig. 10. Once again we notice that for mesh 1, the C_f profiles are in line with reference on the pressure side but far off on the suction side. For mesh 2 ($y^+ \approx 5$), we notice the C_f performing much better on the suction side. In particular the upcoming boundary layer upstream of the LSB location is in line with the Nektar++ reference. However the LSB is still not captured and the wall shear stress after the transition to turbulence remains inaccurate. As we refine one level more (mesh 7 with $y^+ \approx 1$) we notice the appearance of the LSB on the suction side of the 1st flap. However it appears that the transition to turbulence happens earlier than in the reference results.

(a) C_f magnitude

(b) C_f x component

Figure 10: Mean Wall Shear Stress on the 1st Flap.

As seen in Fig. 11, mesh 1 performs poorly on the pressure and suction side of the 2nd flap. As we refine the mesh to $y^+ \approx 5$ (mesh 2), we appear to capture well the C_f on the suction side until $x = -0.46m$, where the flow becomes turbulent without the presence of an LSB. On the pressure side we notice a small negative $C_{f,x}$ component indicating a recirculation region. As we refine further to $y^+ \approx 1$, we notice that the C_f on the suction side diverges from the coarser mesh solution after $x = -0.46m$ and is more in line with the reference Nektar++ results. On the pressure side the LSB can be noticed clearly by the mean $C_{f,x}$ being negative at $y^+ \approx 1$ resolution.

Figure 11: Mean Wall Shear Stress on the 2nd Flap.

4.1.4 Main Takeaways for Hypothesis 1

Based on these results we conclude that $y^+ \approx 5$ (i.e. within the viscous sublayer) is necessary to capture the C_f upstream of the laminar separation bubbles correctly. However $y^+ \approx 1$ is necessary to capture the LSBs on both flaps, while potentially even further resolution is required for the mainplane which has a very compressed LSB because of the effect of the wing being close to the floor.

4.2 Hypothesis 2 (Wall Normal Resolution $y^+ < 1$)

Hypothesis 2 states that even more wall normal resolution is necessary to capture the LSB. This hypothesis is put forward because we observed that as we went from high y^+ to $y^+ \approx 1$ (hypothesis 1) we managed to capture the LSB on the 1st flap but not on the mainplane. We therefore assume that the LSB on the mainplane requires even more resolution since the adverse pressure gradient is stronger and the LSB is thinner.

For this test we dropped the 1st cell height by a factor 2 while increasing the tangential cell size by a factor 2, thus increasing the aspect ratio from 5 to 20.

In Fig. 12a we show the instantaneous wall shear stress x on the suction side and compare it with Mesh 7. As can be observed the spanwise symmetric behaviour is destroyed since the transition location is not consistent across the span. If we look at the mean field in Fig. 12b, we see that this behaviour is consistent in time and not just related to a particular time step.

Figure 12: X component of wall shear stress on the suction side

This appears to indicate that high aspect ratio boundary layer mesh elements run on CharLES perform very poorly. Further confirmation on the impact of the aspect ratio is carried out in section 4.7.

4.3 Hypothesis 3 (CAD Quality)

In this very short section, we verify whether the STL quality has an impact on the stripy behaviour of the wall shear stress on the suction side and whether the transition location is affected. The solution on the better quality STL is restarted from the coarser STL solution file.

Figure 13: Instantaneous wall shear stress magnitude. On Mesh 7 ($y^+ \approx 1$ and aspect ratio 5), the quality of the STL doesn't appear to have impacted the transition location, however the stripped pattern in the higher curved front part of the wing elements is significantly damped.

As can be seen in Fig. 13, the stripy pattern in the wall shear stress is significantly damped by the finer STL. However the transition location indicated by the red line doesn't appear to be impacted. We will therefore run all the simulations with the improved STL to help make results more smooth despite not having helped us converge towards the Nektar++ reference.

4.4 Hypothesis 4, 5, 6 and 7

In this section, we will demonstrate that at WRLES resolution (Mesh 7) no impact can be observed in the solution as we verify the following hypothesis. NB : All simulation are restarted from the baseline Mesh 7 results with Algebraic Wall Model and the higher quality STL.

4.4.1 Hypothesis 4 (Algebraic Wall Model)

For hypothesis 4, we verify whether the usage of the WALL or WM_ALG boundary condition has any impact on the solutions at $y^+ \approx 1$ resolution. We hypothesise that at $y^+ \approx 1$ resolution no significant difference can be expected. To verify this, we simply change the boundary conditions (from WM_ALG to WALL) on the surface of the wing elements of IFW and restart from the last solution with the WALL boundary condition.

4.4.2 Hypothesis 5 (Sub Grid Scale Model)

For hypothesis 5, we verify whether the choice of a sub grid scale model (SGS model) can impact the transition location. For this test we switch from the default Vreman SGS model to SGS_model = None and similarly restart from the version with the Vreman SGS model.

4.4.3 Hypothesis 6 (Time Step Size)

For hypothesis 6, we verify the impact of lowering the time step. In order to verify whether the time step has a significant impact, we lower the time step by a factor 4 (200'000 time steps/CTU instead of 50'000 time steps/CTU).

4.4.4 Hypothesis 7 (Side Wall Boundary Condition)

For hypothesis 7, we verify the impact of changing the side wall boundary condition from slip wall to periodic. We hypothesize that the impact will be minimal especially at the centerline.

Hypothesis 4, 5, 6 and 7 are grouped together since the results overlap very well.

4.4.5 Lift and Drag Coefficients

Firstly we observe the difference between the lift and drag signals as shown in Fig. 14a and 14b. As can be seen, the drag coefficient doesn't appear to be impacted by any of the changes (Algebraic wall model, sub grid scale model, time step size, periodic vs slip side wall) since the two mean values with their respective standard deviations have a very significant overlap (less than half a standard deviation and 0.5% relative difference). For lift, we observe the same behaviour except for the periodic vs slip side wall boundary condition which impacts the mean lift coefficient marginally (1% relative change) but noticeable nevertheless since this difference is larger than the standard deviation of the signals.

Figure 14: Integrated Forces Coefficient Signal

4.4.6 C_p and C_f Profiles

In this section we briefly compare the non-dimensional pressure and skin friction coefficient in order to highlight the minimal differences coming from hypothesis 4,5,6 and 7.

In Fig. 15a we compare the five different simulations with the Nektar++ reference C_p profile and demonstrate that none of the changes help us converge towards the reference. In fact the differences between the five simulations run on Mesh 7 are negligible which explains why the mean integrated forces are all within 1% of each other.

In Fig. 15b we compare the C_f magnitude profile obtained from the five various simulations with the Nektar++ reference. As can be noticed, the CharLES simulations on Mesh 7 overlap very well with negligible differences between each other. All of the simulations predict an earlier transition to turbulence than the Nektar++ reference. Notice also that none of the simulations reach $C_f = 0$ meaning that the mean flow is always attached (no LSB).

Figure 15: Averaged centerline profile on the mainplane. Minimal differences observed.

4.4.7 Point Probe

Since no significant impact was observed in the previous subsection, we shall compare the signal observed at probe locations (i.e. temporal series at the nearest cell centroid) at the surface of the IFW.

In Fig. 16 we compare the U_x velocity component at probe 7 on the suction side of the mainplane ($x = -0.73$ or $x/c \approx 0.47$). We can observe that the energy spectrum of all simulations are identical. All the probes have the $-5/3$ power law over a certain range that corresponds to the inertial range followed by the dissipation range where the turbulent kinetic energy decays significantly. We can also see that probability distribution of the velocity signal is "always" positive (attached flow) and with quasi perfect overlap of the histograms. Finally the temporal auto-correlation functions all have similar exponential decay over short time frame. The exponent of the decay $e^{-\lambda t}$ indicates the correlation length λ which is an estimate for the integral time scale. At longer time scales the function starts oscillating around zero indicating that two instances $u_x(t_0)$ and $u_x(t_0 + t)$ are statically independent if $t \gg \lambda$. All of these plots highlight that we have attached turbulent flow at probe location 7 (on Mesh 7) and that the turbulent statistics are "identical".

Figure 16: Compare velocity probe data at probe location 7. Quasi perfect overlap of all the simulations.

Other probe locations have different behaviour (spectrum, auto-correlation) since the flow is laminar at other locations, however at all probe locations there is near perfect overlap of all the different options on Mesh 7.

4.4.8 Main Takeaways for Hypothesis 4,5,6 and 7

Overall we conclude this subsection by stating that the following changes/comparisons

- IFW Boundary Condition : Wall vs Algebraic Wall Model BC
- Sub Grid Scale Model : Vreman vs None
- Time Step : 50'000 time steps/CTU vs 200'000 time steps/CTU
- Side Wall BC : Euler slip wall vs periodic

have minimal impacts on the results at WRLES resolution (Mesh 7) and are not the reason for being unable to capture the LSB on the mainplane suction side. Only changing the side wall BC has a minimal but noticeable difference. The figures illustrating the impact on the wake velocity profiles are put in the Appendix since the impact is minimal.

4.5 Hypothesis 8

Having tried several settings on a highly resolved mesh (Mesh 7 with 87 million cells), we theorise that the aspect ratio used in Mesh 7 might be too high ($AS = 5$). In fact when we ran simulations with even higher aspect ratios (Mesh 12 with $AS = 20$) we noticed that the results got much worse. Hence why we hypothesise that lowering the aspect ratio below 5 might improve results.

4.5.1 Lift and Drag Coefficient

To evaluate whether the lower aspect ratio and lower growth rate Mesh 32 performs better, let's start off the comparison with the integrated forces obtained. As can be seen by looking at the drag coefficient signals in Fig. 17 we observe a convergence towards the reference value with the relative error for Mesh 32 being about 4%. In Fig. 17 we also compare the energy spectrum of the simulations of the four different meshes. The main feature that we notice with Mesh 32 is the appearance of sharp peaks in the spectrum which didn't appear for the coarser meshes.

Figure 17: Illustrating the drag coefficient signal after reaching a statistically stationary state.

For lift, we observe in Fig. 18 a non monotone convergence of the lift coefficient with Mesh 2 being further away from the reference compared to Mesh 1. Mesh 32 is slightly closer to the reference than the previous meshes ran in hypothesis 1 with slip side walls. If we look at the spectrum we observe the same sharp peaks for Mesh 32 unlike the other meshes. By zooming in we can verify that the strouhal number associated to these peaks corresponds to $St = 25, 38$ and 53 . Slaughter [1] reported peaks but at somewhat different frequencies of $St = 30, 40, 60, 140$ and 200 . A more detailed analysis of the spectrum of each wing element would need to be carried out to verify where the frequencies come from and what causes them.

Figure 18: Illustrating the lift coefficient signal after reaching a statistically stationary state.

4.5.2 C_p and C_f Profiles

As already stated, looking at the integrated forces isn't sufficient to determine whether the results are good since two errors might cancel each other out. As such the centerline pressure coefficient C_p and skin friction coefficient C_f profiles are a far better metric to assess the accuracy of the solver and whether a mesh provides better results.

In Fig. 19a, we show the results obtained with the previous meshes used in hypothesis 1 (Mesh 1, Mesh 2 and Mesh 7) and compare them against the new mesh (Mesh 32) on the mainplane. Unlike the previous meshes, Mesh 32 is able of capturing the flattening of C_p after $x = -0.75$ and then the sharp increase of C_p at the LSB location similarly to the reference, thus indicating that the LSB might finally be captured. A similar behaviour is observed for the 1st flap (see Fig. 29 in the Appendix). For the 2nd flap (see Fig. 19b), no significant impact appears on the suction side which is already well captured with the coarser meshes. On the pressure side, Mesh 32 doesn't appear to bring any improvement since Mesh 7 was already able to capture the LSB albeit at an earlier location compared to the reference.

Figure 19: Illustrating the improvement in the average C_p obtained with Mesh 32

To conclusively demonstrate that Mesh 32 captures the LSB correctly unlike Mesh 7, we should now look at the skin friction coefficient C_f and x-component of C_f in order to verify the re-circulation regions. Since re-circulation regions have negative $C_{f,x}$ let's first verify if the three LSBs appear with the new mesh. In Fig 20, we observe that Mesh 32 does identify three re-circulation regions highlighted in purple that correspond to the LSB on the suction side of the mainplane, the LSB on the suction side of the 1st flap and the LSB on the pressure side of the 2nd flap. The other negative $C_{f,x}$ near the leading edge of each element can be explained by the fact the stagnation point is above the leading edge causing the flow to move against the inlet flow direction in order to pass under the mainplane. When comparing Mesh 32 with Mesh 7, we observe that 2nd flap LSB is captured just as well, the 1st flap LSB appears on Mesh 7 but is very diffused and more upstream, while for the mainplane Mesh 7 fails to capture the LSB unlike Mesh 32. This shows that the LSB on the mainplane is the hardest to capture. After each of the three LSB we notice that $C_{f,x}$ increases sharply and becomes positive thus highlighting the re-attachment of the flow and the transition to turbulence.

In Fig. 30 in the Appendix, we compare the instantaneous and time averaged x-component of wall shear stress for Mesh 7 and Mesh 32.

Figure 20: Average C_f x-component on all three wing elements obtained with CharLES solver

Having just shown that Mesh 32 captures the LSBs on all three wing elements as expected, let's now compare the C_f magnitude with the Nektar++ reference to see if the locations of the LSB and the laminar to turbulent transition matches those given by the reference. In Fig. 21, we observe that the latest mesh is able to reach $C_f = 0$ before transitioning sharply to turbulence. The transition location does however appear to be about 1cm earlier than for Nektar++. This is nevertheless much closer than the transition location obtained with Mesh 7.

Figure 21: Average C_f on the mainplane obtained on four meshes and comparison with Nektar++ reference.

For the 1st flap, we observe a similar behaviour with the latest mesh once again predicting the LSB and a later transition location which is more in line with the Nektar++ reference. Once the flow has transitioned to turbulence the skin friction magnitudes are very similar between Mesh 32 and the WRLES Nektar++ results. For the 2nd flap, we observe the opposite trend with Mesh 32 performing worse than Mesh 7. On the pressure side, both Mesh 7 and Mesh 32 predict the LSB correctly and the differences downstream remain negligible. On the suction side, we see that Mesh 32 performs worse with Mesh 7 agreeing much better with the Nektar++ reference.

(a) 1st Flap : Transition to turbulence moves back- (b) 2nd Flap : Mesh 7 appears to match the suction
wards with Mesh 32 side profile better than Mesh 32

Figure 22: Averaged centerline C_f profile

4.6 Main takeaways for hypothesis 8

Based on the improved results obtained with Mesh 32 the following conclusions can be made

- Mesh 32 can capture the mainplane LSB unlike Mesh 7
- $y^+ \approx 1$ isn't necessary to capture the mainplane LSB since Mesh 32 has a peak $y^+ \approx 2.5$ at the transition location which is higher than Mesh 7 ($y^+ \approx 1$).
- x^+ and z^+ are kept the same for Mesh 7 and Mesh 32, therefore the absence of the LSB in Mesh 7 isn't related to resolution at the wall but potentially caused by some undesirable effect caused by the higher aspect ratios.
- The mainplane LSB height is measured to be approximately $y^+ \approx 12$, which explains why WMLES fails, since several cell points are necessary across the height of the LSB in order to represent it. Mesh 32 has 4 cell across the height of the LSB, which far fewer than Mesh 7 which didn't capture the LSB but more than Mesh 1 and Mesh 2 which didn't capture the LSB.
- The number of STRAND elements was increased from 12 (Mesh 7) to 20 (Mesh 32), this results in a taller structured STRAND mesh and a much lower growth ratio. The last element in the STRAND has aspect ratio 1, hence why the growth rate is decreases implicitly by increasing the number of boundary layer elements in the STRAND.

With these main takeaways and open questions, an investigation on the effect of the aspect ratio and the growth rate is carried out in the next section.

4.7 Aspect Ratio and Growth Rate Investigation

Since we just demonstrate that Mesh 32 ($y^+ = 2.5$, $AS = 2$, $G = 1.036$ and 20 elements across the structured BL height) captures the physics properly, we now wish to understand better how we could potentially coarsen the mesh and still obtain excellent results with LES. In fact Mesh 32 has both a very low aspect ratio ($AS = 2$) and a very low growth rate ($G = 1.036$) which would make accurate WRLES extremely expensive on the full 3D IFW.

In order to investigate further the effect of the aspect ratio, the growth rate and the number of layers, multiple meshes were generated : Mesh 33, 34, 35 and 36. All the simulations were restarted from the results obtained on Mesh 7, which did not capture the mainplane LSB.

NB : The results shown here are incomplete since they have not been run for long enough. These results have not been averaged over the average 8 CTUs like the previous results. However if the LSB is visible on any of these simulations we can consider that the accuracy has been improved significantly since we are restarted from Mesh 7 (did not capture the mainplane LSB) rather than Mesh 32 (did capture the LSB).

4.7.1 Lift and Drag Coefficient

Despite not having had enough time to run all the simulation for the necessary 8 CTUs averaging time, we show in Fig. 23 the lift and drag signal obtained so far for completeness purposes. In Fig. 23a, we observe overall minimal impact on the drag coefficient with Mesh 32, Mesh 33, Mesh 34, Mesh 35 and Mesh 36 all being within one standard deviation (less than 2% relative error or 3 drag counts) of each other. Only Mesh 7 is more than one standard deviation away from the other highly resolved simulations. For the lift coefficient as shown in Fig. 23b, the differences are somewhat more noticeable although a longer simulation time appears necessary to reach a statically stationary state. We can observe that Mesh 33 appears to be moving away from the reference Nektar++ and statically stationary results obtained with CharLES (Mesh 32).

Overall not too much should be read into the integrated forces firstly because they are not fully converged and secondly because we don't know yet where the differences are coming from. To verify this we show the C_p profile in the next section.

Figure 23: Integrated Forces Signal

4.7.2 C_p and C_f Profiles

In this section, we highlight how the aspect ratio, growth rate, and first cell height impact both the pressure coefficient C_p and the skin friction coefficient C_f in the areas where the most resolution is required (i.e. mainplane suction, particularly near the LSB location). In Fig. 24a, we compare the mean centerline pressure coefficient C_p near the LSB and laminar to turbulent transition for the various mesh resolutions. Overall we see that Mesh 32 and Mesh 35 appear to be the most in line with the Nektar++ reference. For Mesh 34 and 36 the pressure recovery appears to be marginally shifted forwards, while for Mesh 7 and Mesh 33 this pressure recovery feature appears to be totally diffused.

In Fig. 24b, we compare the mean skin friction coefficient C_f of the various meshes. Once again we notice that Mesh 7 and Mesh 33 appear to be the furthest away from the Nektar++ reference and in particular never reach $C_f = 0$ on the mainplane suction side ($x \approx -0.75$). This indicates that both Mesh 7 and Mesh 33 do not capture the laminar separation bubble which explains why the C_p profiles were also inaccurate. Mesh 32, Mesh 34, Mesh 35 and Mesh 36 all appear to show $C_f = 0$ and thus indicating that the LSB is captured followed by a sharp increase in skin friction which corresponds to the laminar to turbulent transition location. Based on the profiles it appears that the highly resolved CharLES meshes predict this location earlier than Slaughter [1]. The exact location being further upstream could be mesh related or potentially setup related since Slaughter does not treat the spanwise direction the same way as us (Fourier modes in third dimension).

Figure 24: Averaged centerline profile on the mainplane

In Fig. 25 we illustrate the time averaged x-component of skin friction coefficient C_f for the various meshes. A negative value of $C_{f,x}$ shows a re-circulation zone which we expect when looking for a laminar separation bubble. On the mainplane (Fig. 25a) we observe the Mesh 7 and Mesh 33 do not capture the LSB, while Mesh 34 doesn't capture the location correctly. Mesh 32, Mesh 35 and Mesh 36 appear to be converging towards a similar LSB location and laminar to turbulence transition location. On the 1st flap however (Fig. 25b), we notice that only Mesh 33 doesn't capture a LSB on the suction side. But Mesh 7 and Mesh 34 capture a LSB albeit further upstream compared to the more resolved meshes (Mesh 32, Mesh 35 and Mesh 36). This appears to show that the meshing criterion necessary to capture the LSB is more stringent on the mainplane than the 1st flap. This is most likely because the mainplane is closer to the ground and has therefore a more compressed boundary layer and laminar separation bubble which requires more mesh resolution.

Figure 25: Averaged x-component of C_f centerline profile

4.7.3 Velocity Profiles at Laminar Separation Bubble Location

In this subsection, we briefly compare the u_x velocity profile were the laminar separation bubble should be present on the mainplane suction side.

In Fig. 26 we clearly see that Mesh 7, Mesh 33 and Mesh 34 do not predict the LSB, while Mesh 32, Mesh 35 and Mesh 37 predict it correctly. The line in blue corresponds to the approximate LSB bubble height $y/c \approx 0.001$ reported by Slaughter [1] which appears to match relatively well with the predictions from the low aspect ratio and low growth rate meshes. This very thin LSB height is the reason why WMLES performed poorly since the first cell height isn't close enough to represent the bubble.

Figure 26: u_x velocity profile at the LSB location ($x = -0.73$ or $x/c \approx 0.44$) on the suction side of the mainplane.

In Fig. 26 we also see that the differences between the velocity profiles decreases significantly as we move further than 1cm away from the surface of the IFW. We can thus assume that the STRAND height has not affected but rather the differences come from the inner boundary layer differences.

4.7.4 Main Takeaways for Aspect Ratio and Growth Rate Investigation

In this section we demonstrated the following

- The comparison between Mesh 32, Mesh 33 and Mesh 34 which all have the first cell height and aspect ratio 2, shows that the meshes with fewer STRAND elements (i.e higher growth rates) do not capture the LSB. Mesh 33 which has a growth rate $G = 1.12$ does not capture the mainplane LSB, Mesh 34 ($G = 1.08$) captures a very diffused mainplane LSB which is also too far upstream and Mesh 32 ($G = 1.036$) is able to capture the LSB very well.
- Mesh 7 also fails most likely because of the growth rate of 1.16. In fact Mesh 36 has the same first cell height and aspect ratio 5, but is able to capture the mainplane LSB thanks to a much lower growth rate.
- Differences become less meaningful as we move away from the wall.

These findings are summarised in Table 4.

Simulation	y^+	Metrics					Mainplane LSB
		Aspect Ratio	Nb Layers Profile	Growth Rate	Cells within LSB height		
Mesh 1	15-20	2	10	1.08	0	LSB not captured	
Mesh 2	5	5	10	1.2	2	LSB not captured	
Mesh 7	1	5	12	1.16	7	LSB not captured (recirculation zone seen in instantaneous wall shear stress but not the mean)	
Mesh 32	2.5	2	20	1.036	4	LSB captured with good location	
Mesh 33	2.5	2	7	1.12	3	LSB not captured (recirculation zone seen in instantaneous wall shear stress but not the mean)	
Mesh 34	2.5	2	10	1.08	4	LSB appears but very diffused and too far upstream	
Mesh 35	1.6	3	20	1.06	6	LSB captured with good location	
Mesh 36	1	5	20	1.088	8	LSB captured with good location	

Table 4: Table summarising the effect of the first cell height, aspect ratio, growth rate, etc... on the accurate capture of the laminar separation bubble on the mainplane suction side

4.8 Wake Velocity Profile

In this section, the wake velocity profiles are illustrated to demonstrate how significantly the wake velocity profile is impacted by the near wall mesh resolution. Only the boundary layer mesh resolution is changed, the wake mesh refined is kept identical through the simulations. Fig. 27 shows the comparison of the U_x velocity profile (mean and standard deviation) for the various meshes and compares them against the results obtained by Slaughter [1]. We see that the coarsest mesh (Mesh 1) predicts a wake momentum deficit that is about $0.1c$ lower than the more wall resolved simulations which match the reference very well. When looking at the $U_{x,rms}$ we notice some larger difference but generally good qualitative agreement.

Figure 27: Wake momentum deficit $x/c = 2$ behind the the leading edge of the mainplane. Comparison of the wake as we resolve the boundary layer (wake refinement unchanged). The standard deviation is illustrated for one of the simulations to indicate the fluctuation amplitude.

Further downstream, we observe a similar behaviour. In Fig. 28, we illustrate these differences 6 chord lengths behind the leading edge of the mainplane. Once again we observe that Mesh 1 predicts a wake momentum deficit that is lower than the more mesh refined simulations. The other meshes correctly predict the peak momentum deficit location ($z/c \approx 0.95 - 1$) albeit with a slightly higher minimal velocity. When comparing the $U_{x,rms}$ we notice good agreement both near the moving floor and in the wake of wing elements.

Figure 28: Wake momentum deficit $x/c = 6$ behind the the leading edge of the mainplane. Comparison of the wake as we resolve the boundary layer (wake refinement unchanged). The standard deviation is illustrated for one of the simulations to indicate the fluctuation amplitude.

For both of these locations we observe that the capturing of the LSB by Mesh 32 does not impact the wake significantly compared to the coarser Mesh 2 and Mesh 7, particularly when taking the variance in the signal into account. It does however appear as though placing a first cell height in the viscous sub-layer ($y^+ \approx 5$) does improve our results. The figures for the other locations are placed in the Appendix.

5 Discussion / Mesh Recommendations / Best Practices

In this section, we summarise the results obtained throughout this investigation. In order to capture certain flow features with the CharLES solver, the following meshing recommendations can be given:

- Upcoming laminar flow : To capture the upcoming laminar flow, we need to place the first cell height at $y^+ \approx 5$ (Mesh 2), which corresponds to the viscous sub-layer
- Laminar to turbulent transition : To capture the laminar to turbulent, we need to once again place the first height at $y^+ \approx 5$ (Mesh 2). The transition location will however be too early unless the resolution is sufficient to also accurately capture the laminar separation bubble (LSB).
- Mainplane LSB : The mainplane has a measured height of $y^+ \approx 12$ or $y/c \approx 0.001$. This means that a low y^+ mesh is necessary simply to represent the curvature of the velocity field.
 - Mesh 32 demonstrated that $y^+ \approx 1$ is not necessary since Mesh 32 ($y^+ \approx 2.5$) was able to capture the mainplane LSB.
 - At least 4 cells across the height of the mainplane LSB appear to be necessary (see Mesh 32) to represent the LSB and avoid it being totally diffused.
 - Aspect ratio : An aspect ratio of 5 was the highest used that was able to capture the LSB correctly (Mesh 36).
 - Growth rate : A growth rate of 1.088 was the highest used that was able to capture the LSB correctly (Mesh 36).
- LSB on the 1st and 2nd flap : To capture the LSB on the 1st and 2nd flap, similar meshing criteria should be used. These can however be relaxed since the LSB is less thin compared to the mainplane LSB, because it is further away from the moving floor. Mesh 7 for example captures the LSBs on the flaps but not on the mainplane, albeit further upstream than the more highly resolved Mesh 32.

The impact of factors that are not mesh related are the follows :

- STL / CAD quality (Hypothesis 2) : The quality of the imported STL file does not appear to impact the results as shown by the comparison on Mesh 7.
- Algebraic Wall Model (Hypothesis 4) : At WRLES resolution, we showed that using the solver with wall model active converges towards the same solution as setting the boundary condition to no slip wall.
- Sub Grid Scale Model (Hypothesis 5) : At WRLES resolution, the choice of the sub grid scale model has minimal impact (see the verification of hypothesis 5 on Mesh 7).
- Time Step Size (Hypothesis 6) : In hypothesis 6, we showed that on highly resolved mesh (Mesh 7) keeping the time step such that $CFL \approx 1$ is sufficient since lowering the time step by a factor 4 had a negligible impact.
- Slip Wall vs Periodic Side Walls (Hypothesis 7) : In hypothesis 7, we showed that changing the side wall boundary condition does not impact the centerline profiles, but does impact the edges marginally causing a measurable shift in the integrated forces.

A table summarising the results obtained at the different mesh resolutions is given in Table 5, which shows that as we resolve the boundary layer we obtain the correct near wall flow physics.

Metrics				
Simulation	C_L	C_D	C_f Profile	LSB mainplane
CharLES WMLLES (Mesh 1, $y^+ \approx 15$)	-8.11	0.207	upcoming laminar BL not captured correctly, flow is fully turbulent	LSB NOT captured
CharLES WMLLES (Mesh 2, $y^+ \approx 5$)	-8.03	-0.191 (12% diff. to ref)	Upcoming laminar boundary layer and laminar to turbulent transition captured. However the transition is too early	LSB NOT captured
CharLES WR-LES (Mesh 7, $y^+ \approx 1, AS = 5$)	-8.20	0.184 (8% diff. to ref)	Upcoming BL and laminar to turbulent transition captured. Early transition and LSB not captured.	LSB NOT captured in the mean flow, however small re-circulation zones can be seen moving downstream in the instantaneous flow field at $St \approx 66$
CharLES WR-LES (Mesh 32, $y^+ \approx 2.5, AS = 2$)	-8.21 (1.5% diff. to ref)	0.177 (4% diff. to ref)	very good agreement with reference (slightly earlier transition on mainplane)	LSB captured. Small re-circulation zones move downstream at frequency of $St \approx 50$
Nektar++ (ref)	-8.33	0.17	reference	LSB captured

Table 5: Performance on key metrics for the extruded IFW. Colors indicate relative performance.

The following steps should be taken to complete the investigation

- Run Mesh 33, 34, 35 and 36 for the full 8 CTUs averaging window
- Apply the mesh findings to the full 3D Imperial Front Wing

Conclusion

In this study we showed how well the FV LES CharLES solver performs for the extruded 2D Imperial Front Wing. We started off running the code at a resolution that would require the usage of wall models, before gradually refining the mesh to achieve wall resolved LES simulation with CharLES. This is hypothesis 1 which states that we require $y^+ = 1$ to properly capture the physics of the laminar separation bubble and the transition. Unfortunately this didn't prove to be sufficient. While the LSBs in time averaged sense are visible on the suction side of the first flap and also on the pressure side on the 2nd flap, it still does not appear on the suction side of the mainplane. A whole set of hypothesis were tested to verify whether the incapacity of Mesh 7 to capture the laminar separation bubble might have been caused by factors that were not mesh related. We verified the effect of the imported STL CAD file, the usage of algebraic wall model vs the wall boundary condition at $y^+ = 1$, the effect of the sub grid scale model, the time step size and the side walls (slip vs periodic) and demonstrated that the inability to capture the mainplane LSB was not caused by any of these factors (sections 4.3 and 4.4). In section 4.5 we tried to lower the aspect ratio and the growth rate, since we had previously obtained very poor results in section 4.2 when using high aspect ratio ($AS = 20$). This resulted in us being able to capture the LSB on all three wing elements and match the physics obtained by Slaughter [1] with the WRLES Nektar++ code. Thereafter, in section 4.7 we proceeded to investigate the effect of the growth rate and the aspect ratio. Here we showed that aspect ratios of 5 can be used with CharLES (see Mesh 36) to produce accurate results and that higher growth rates do not appear to be able to capture the LSB. Table 4 summarises the results on the aspect ratio and growth rate investigation, although further tests should be carried out. Regarding the momentum deficit of the velocity profiles in the wake, we observe a significant improvement when lowering the first cell height to $y^+ \approx 5$ (inside viscous sub-layer). Clear further improvement are not noticed by fully resolving the near wall physics.

To conclude, we can state that while Wall Resolved LES is necessary to capture the near wall physics, this resolution is not necessary to capture the flow field in the wake which is on primary interest for F1 teams to capture the shape and strength of the vortices being created.

Appendix

Figure 29: Average C_p on 1st Flap

(a) Mesh 7 : Re-circulation zones (in blue) appear in the instantaneous wall shear stress, but not in the time average field.

(b) Mesh 32 : Thicker re-circulation zones (in blue) appear in the instantaneous wall shear stress. However, unlike for Mesh 7, a re-circulation zone also appears in the time averaged field on the mainplane.

Figure 30: Comparison of the x component of wall shear stress for Mesh 7 and Mesh 32 together with the velocity profile of the boundary layer on the suction side of the mainplane.

Figure 31: Wake momentum deficit $x/c = 2$ behind the the leading edge of the mainplane. Comparison of the mean and variance with all the parameters on Mesh 7 against the reference [1]

Figure 32: Wake momentum deficit $x/c = 2.5$ behind the the leading edge of the mainplane. Comparison of the mean and variance with all the parameters on Mesh 7 against the reference [1]

Figure 33: Wake momentum deficit $x/c = 4$ behind the the leading edge of the mainplane. Comparison of the mean and variance with all the parameters on Mesh 7 against the reference [1]

Figure 34: Wake momentum deficit $x/c = 6$ behind the the leading edge of the mainplane. Comparison of the mean and variance with all the parameters on Mesh 7 against the reference [1]

Figure 35: Wake momentum deficit $x/c = 2$ behind the the leading edge of the mainplane. Comparison of the wake as we resolve the boundary layer (wake refinement unchanged).

Figure 36: Wake momentum deficit $x/c = 2.5$ behind the the leading edge of the mainplane. Comparison of the wake as we resolve the boundary layer (wake refinement unchanged).

Figure 37: Wake momentum deficit $x/c = 4$ behind the the leading edge of the mainplane. Comparison of the wake as we resolve the boundary layer (wake refinement unchanged).

Figure 38: Wake momentum deficit $x/c = 6$ behind the the leading edge of the mainplane. Comparison of the wake as we resolve the boundary layer (wake refinement unchanged).

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